

Optimizing Multi-Task Learning for Accurate Spacecraft Pose Estimation

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Accurate satellite pose estimation is crucial for autonomous guidance, navigation, and control (GNC) systems in in-orbit servicing (IOS) missions. This paper explores the impact of different tasks within a multi-task learning (MTL) framework for satellite pose estimation using monocular images. By integrating tasks such as direct pose estimation, keypoint prediction, object localization, and segmentation into a single network, the study aims to evaluate the reciprocal influence between tasks by testing different multi-task configurations thanks to the modularity of the convolutional neural network (CNN) used in this work. The trends of mutual bias between the analyzed tasks are found by employing different weighting strategies to further test the robustness of the findings. A synthetic dataset was developed to train and test the MTL network. Results indicate that direct pose estimation and heatmap-based pose estimation positively influence each other in general, while both the bounding box and segmentation tasks do not provide significant contributions and tend to degrade the overall estimation accuracy.

1 Introduction

Autonomous guidance, navigation, and control (GNC) systems are crucial for in-orbit servicing (IOS) missions, enabling tasks such as docking, repair, and refuelling. Accurate satellite pose estimation is essential for these operations. Traditional methods using multiple sensors like lidar and stereo cameras increase complexity and cost. This paper focuses on using monocular cameras for satellite pose estimation to streamline the process while maintaining high accuracy.

Recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI), particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have significantly improved computer vision tasks. However, monocular vision systems face limitations in scale ambiguity and depth perception, necessitating sophisticated algorithms for high precision [1–3].

Multi-task learning (MTL) allows a single model to learn multiple related tasks simultaneously, leverag-

ing shared representations to improve performance and efficiency [4, 5]. In satellite pose estimation, MTL can integrate direct pose estimation, keypoint detection, object detection, and segmentation into a unified framework, optimizing inference time and resource utilization.

A key development in this field is the Spacecraft Pose Network v2 (SPNv2)[6], which uses a multi-scale, multi-task CNN architecture to perform object detection, keypoint prediction, binary segmentation, and direct pose estimation. This approach has shown improved robustness and accuracy over previous methods. Moreover, SPNv2 has inspired the present research.

This paper explores the potential of MTL for satellite pose estimation using monocular cameras. By integrating various tasks into a single network, we aim to enhance the performance and efficiency of pose estimation systems for IOS missions. Our contributions include:

- Developing a synthetic dataset generation pipeline for training, validation, and testing.
- Implementing a modular MTL network that outputs direct pose estimation, keypoint prediction, object detection, and segmentation from a single input image.
- Evaluating the MTL network's performance to demonstrate its advantages over single-task learning and provide evidence for a task selection strategy to avoid negative and suboptimal setups.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Synthetic Data Generation

Our dataset generation leverages a proprietary Unity-based setup, enabling the creation of both random and trajectory-based images of a satellite. This setup

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Figure 1: Two samples from our dataset. Each row corresponds to a sample. The first column contains the generated capture. The second column shows the bounding box. The third column displays the keypoints' heatmap. The fourth column contains the segmentation masks.

allows for a diverse range of scenarios and lighting conditions, providing a robust dataset essential for training and evaluating our multi-task learning (MTL) models.

For this work, we generated 40,000 images of the Tango satellite, split into 70%-20%-10% for training, validation and testing. The dataset was randomized within a range of 1 to 25 meters to simulate various operational distances and orientations. The camera setup used for image generation included a resolution of 1024×1024 pixels, a focal length of 39.47 mm, and a pixel pitch of $5.86 \mu\text{m}/\text{px}$. The horizontal and vertical fields of view were both set to 35.0 degrees. The images were rescaled to 512×512 pixels to make training and inference more feasible.

The dataset includes detailed metadata for each image, consisting of the pose of the satellite relative to the camera, the projected location of the 18 keypoints (differently from the 11 keypoints used in [6]) distributed across the satellite on the camera frame, the bounding box of the satellite, and a binary segmentation mask. The keypoints in 2D locations are used to generate heatmaps used as ground-truths. The Tango satellite model is chosen as the target body in the foreground, while the background includes simulated space environments, providing a realistic and challenging dataset for our models. Some dataset samples from the test set are displayed in Figure 1.

2.2 Model Architecture and Setup

The developed network architecture is designed to handle multiple tasks from a single input image: di-

rect pose estimation, indirect pose estimation via keypoint prediction, bounding box estimation, and segmentation mask.

The network utilizes an EfficientNet [7] backbone for feature extraction and a Bidirectional Feature Pyramid Network (BiFPN) to enhance feature representation across scales. The heads attached to the backbone are EfficientPose [8] for object localization and direct pose estimation, a heatmap head for keypoints prediction, and a segmentation map head for target segmentation.

A key feature of our network implementation is its modularity, which makes it fully configurable. This design allows us to easily activate or deactivate specific tasks, enabling flexible experimentation and optimization. This modular approach is critical to fine-tuning the network and achieving optimal performance for specific tasks. The development framework utilized was PyTorch 2.0 [9].

The network tasks are labelled as follows: direct pose estimation (**P**), indirect pose estimation or heatmap-based pose estimation (**H**), bounding box estimation (**B**), and segmentation estimation (**S**). The indirect pose estimation is obtained by solving the PnP problem by exploiting the predicted keypoints' heatmaps [10]. A representation of the network is presented in Figure 2.

Managing multiple outputs in a MTL network requires effective weighting strategies to balance the importance of each task. This is particularly relevant when tasks are heterogeneous and qualitatively different.

Our setup allows for both manual and automatic

Figure 2: Simplified visualization of the proposed CNN MTL architecture. P, H, B, and S respectively represent the heads for direct pose estimation, keypoints’ heatmaps prediction, bounding box prediction, and segmentation tasks.

task weighting strategies. By default, tasks are assigned equal weighting (**EW**), but other strategies can be employed, including:

- **Random Loss Weighting (RLW)**, which assigns random weights to tasks during each training iteration [11];
- **Dynamic Weight Average (DWA)**, which adjusts task weights dynamically based on the training loss trends [12];
- **Gradient Normalization (GradNorm)**, which normalizes gradients to ensure balanced learning across tasks [13].

In this study, we investigate whether auxiliary tasks aid the primary task of pose estimation, crucial for satellite navigation.

We first train the network with only direct pose estimation (P) as the primary task. Next, we train with all tasks included (PHBS). To assess the impact of each auxiliary task, we use a leave-one-out strategy: excluding heatmap-based pose estimation (PBS), bounding box estimation (PHS), and segmentation estimation (PHB).

We also test configurations by adding each auxiliary task individually to the primary task (P): heatmap-based pose estimation (PH), bounding box estimation (PB), and segmentation estimation (PS).

Finally, to understand the role of auxiliary tasks without direct pose estimation (P), we use heatmap-based pose estimation (H) as the primary task and test combinations with bounding box (HB), segmentation (HS), and both tasks (HSB).

This approach allows us to evaluate the effectiveness of auxiliary tasks in enhancing the primary task of pose estimation.

For evaluating the performance of our pose estimation model, we use the following metrics:

- **Translation Error:** Measures the Euclidean distance between the estimated translation vector \hat{t} and the ground truth translation vector t :

$$E_T = \|\hat{t} - t\|$$

- **Rotation Error:** Quantifies the difference between the estimated rotation matrix \hat{R} and the ground truth rotation matrix R :

$$E_R = \arccos\left(\frac{\text{trace}(\hat{R}R^T) - 1}{2}\right)$$

- **SPEED Score:** A composite metric evaluating overall pose estimation performance by considering both rotation error and normalized translation error:

$$\text{SPEED score} = E_{\text{pose}} = E_R(\hat{R}, R) + \frac{E_T(\hat{t}, t)}{\|t\|}$$

The SPEED score is also used as the loss for the direct pose estimation task. The object localization task is trained by the means of the *Complete Intersection over Union* (C-IoU) loss, while both the keypoints’ heatmaps and target segmentation tasks are associated with a *pixel-wise Mean Squared Error* (MSE) loss.

All the experiments were conducted with a consistent number of training epochs, identical hyperparameters (as detailed in Table 1), with the same batch size (BS) and the same learning rate (LR) decay schedule.

Epochs	BS	LR	LR steps	LR factor
40	16	5×10^{-4}	75% - 90 %	1×10^{-1}

Table 1: Training hyperparameters.

The network’s backbone was scaled down to create a lightweight version, allowing for a high number of experiments. This resulted in the selection of the smallest version of EfficientNet, *EfficientNet-B0*. The number of parameters characterizing the backbone and the prediction heads involved in the experiments are summarized in Table 2.

Since the focus is exclusively on pose estimation, the model size could be reduced for deployment by eliminating all auxiliary heads after they are used for training. Furthermore, these findings could be investigated using alternative, more compact backbones or architectures, potentially reducing the parameter count while preserving performance.

The training sessions were conducted on an NVIDIA RTX A6000 GPU. The chosen number of epochs represents a balance between training duration and the achieved performance in pose estimation.

Network block	Number of parameters
EfficientNet-B0*	3,824,772
P	90,116
H	48,082
B	18,852
D	45,889
Tot.	4,024,711

Table 2: Number of network parameters. The block identified by (*) is the network’s backbone; the other blocks are prediction heads.

Additionally, the optimization of the network’s total loss begins to plateau after 40 epochs, thus further improvements are not considered beneficial to the objectives of this study.

3 Results

In this section, we present the results of our experiments trained and tested to evaluate the effectiveness of our MTL network for spacecraft pose estimation. Our primary objective was to determine whether auxiliary tasks can improve the accuracy of the pose estimation tasks. We begin by evaluating the direct (P) and indirect (H) pose estimation tasks in a single-task setup. This configuration serves as our baseline for comparing the impact of including auxiliary tasks. The results calculated on the test-set are summarized in the form of SPEED score in Table 3.

Model	Median	IQR
P	0.052	0.046
H	0.042	0.035

Table 3: SPEED scores for single task networks P and H.

We tested the direct pose estimation task (P) with various combinations of auxiliary tasks (H, B, S) and different weighting strategies. The configurations include complete multi-task training (PHBS), leave-one-out strategies (PBS, PHS, PHB), and single auxiliary task addition (PH, PB, PS). The results are presented as the percentage improvement in SPEED score relative to the single-task baseline in Figure 3. Percentage changes from baseline results in pose estimation performance provide an immediate and straightforward way to compare the efficacy of different configurations and are more convenient to read than absolute numbers for the SPEED score to highlight variations.

Figure 3: Percentual change in SPEED score from direct pose estimation compared to the single task network P performance. A positive change means a reduction in the score (the lower the better).

In Figure 4, the same is shown for the indirect pose estimation (H).

Figure 4: Percentual change in SPEED score from indirect pose estimation compared to the single task network H performance. A positive change means a reduction in the score (the lower the better).

For the sake of completeness, the qualitative results from the inference on a test image of the PBHS model trained through the equal weighting strategy are displayed in Figure 5.

4 Conclusion and Discussion

The comparative results between single-task direct pose estimation (P) and multi-task learning (MTL) solutions indicate that the indirect pose estimation (H) task is beneficial to the direct one (P). In contrast, bounding box estimation (B) does not significantly impact the results, and segmentation estimation (S) negatively affects the overall pose estimation accuracy.

Figure 5: Inference results on a test sample. The predicted bounding box, heatmaps and segmentation are highlighted in the bottom row, while the relative ground truths are in the upper row.

This negative influence is likely due to the differing nature of the segmentation task compared to the others, which may translate to a different scale for the selected loss.

These findings hold across various weighting strategies, suggesting that different strategies do not substantially alter the overall trend. Among the evaluated methods, Equal Weighting (EW) and Dynamic Weight Average (DWA) were identified as the most effective.

In the context of heatmap-based (indirect) pose estimation (H), the presence of the segmentation task (S) also resulted in degraded performance. Furthermore, H did not generally receive positive contributions from other tasks, except for direct pose estimation (P). This trend was consistent across different weighting strategies, reinforcing the robustness of the results.

Overall, GradNorm was found to be the least effective weighting strategy in our evaluations.

While the effects of the experiments on the indirect pose estimation are limited, revealing some kind of knowledge saturation for the keypoints' heatmap regression task (H), the smallest model to achieve the best SPEED score from the direct estimation task (P) is the PH configuration, trained with the DWA strategy. For this model, a 75% performance boost with respect to the baseline model (P only) leads to a median SPEED score of 0.013. This score value is low when compared to results presented in [6] using the same backbone. This may be partly attributed to the data on which the model is trained, but it is crucial to acknowledge how exploring different network configurations together with diverse weighting strategies led to achieving a 75% enhancement on the direct pose estimation task.

Future work will test the repeatability of the experiments using more domain-representative simulated data for training and testing.

It is to be noticed that the results presented are contingent upon both the global and task-specific config-

urations of the network; variations in individual task losses within the MTL framework can yield differing outcomes. Consequently, these results and experimental setups should be considered as a baseline for upcoming advancements.

Future research will also focus on exploring alternative weighting strategies to optimize the synergy and mutual information embedded within the metadata. Additionally, it can be important to assess the impact of additional types of metadata (e.g., other ground-truths) to enhance the performance and robustness of the multi-task learning framework.

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